

Implementation, Support System and Difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13207696>

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to determine the extent of implementation, level of support system and level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal. The study made use of 42 MAPEH teachers currently employed in the two districts. The extent of implementation, level of support system, and level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal was assessed based on curriculum delivery, teacher development and learning resources. The researcher constructed a survey questionnaire. Descriptive was used in this study. The statistical tools used in the analysis of data were the frequency distribution and percentage, mean, and Mann - Whitney U test. Based on the results of the study, the extent of implementation in the areas of curriculum delivery, teacher development, and learning resources were great. The level of support system in curriculum delivery was great while in teacher development and learning resources was moderate. The level of difficulties in Music was high while in the areas of Arts, PE and Health were moderate. This paper calls for school heads, master teachers, and MAPEH teachers should continue to work together to sustain the implementation and support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal at their respective stations; District and school management should prioritize the improvement and availability of teaching art materials and musical instruments and allocate budget to it; and Division Education Program Supervisor (DEPS) in MAPEH offer seminars and training on the competencies needed.

Keywords: Implementation, support system, MAPEH Programs, new normal, curriculum delivery, teacher development, learning resources

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

MAPEH, which stands for Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health, is one of the topic areas in the K-12 curriculum (Daga, 2021). In fact, Article 14, Section 18 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution, "Education, Science, and Technology, Arts, Culture and Sports," served as the legal foundation for this study's investigation of physical education, emphasizing the need for the state. As for what the two districts are experiencing, there is still a need for more action plans to be addressed on the use of modules, selecting the most relevant topics, assessing learners, and the consistency and uniformity of the platforms in implementing the MAPEH programs in secondary public schools. Moreover, MAPEH teachers are trying to be engaged and updated in various workshops and training in the new normal. Regarding learning resources, MAPEH teachers use social media and other e-learning sources to give sufficient resources to the learners.

In terms of a support system, collaboration is needed for a team to achieve great things. School heads and master teachers in the two districts are still finding interventions, programs, and research to address the teacher's and learners' needs. They are responsible for encouraging teachers to develop their knowledge and skills in their respective fields. They are also finding ways to find smooth access to different learning resources.

In the four main components of MAPEH, difficulties are inevitable. MAPEH teachers are challenged in developing an appropriate contextualized assessment in the four areas. In Music and Arts, instruments and teaching art materials are lacking. Teachers need more time to let the learners perform such skills. In Physical education, teachers are finding active recreation and fun initiatives in learning the subject. In health, practicing safety is hard due to these challenging situations. RM no. 141, s. 2020 or the regional research priority topics in the new normal stated that to address and provide significant and research-based data for teaching and learning, it must be responsive and aligned to the implementation of the essential learning competencies (MELCS), which is the guide for today's curriculum, instruction, and assessment. The implementation, support system, and difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the new normal can be assessed regarding curriculum delivery, teacher development, and learning resources.

The above scenario has motivated the researcher to investigate the issue considering how MAPEH contributes significantly to the holistic development of learners. As MAPEH and Practical Research Teacher at a secondary school, this researcher was motivated to determine the extent of implementation, level of support, and difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the new normal education as a basis for an intervention plan that will be used to attract the concerned authorities to come up with a resolution towards the enhancement of students' learning outcomes.

Current State of Knowledge

Dulay's (2022) study, meanwhile, found that the MAPEH program was implemented to a great extent, with a grand mean of 4.08 from teachers and 3.94 from the school administrators in terms of the program's objectives, curriculum, learning assessment, and resources, teachers' qualification, and competency, administrative support, funding, and community partnership. On the other hand, the Results of Barrera's (2022) investigation revealed that seminars and webinars were neither essential nor helpful in shaping their perspectives on problems; more so, attending training and webinars did not influence how acceptable coping mechanisms were for them which had a similar idea with the result of the study. An investigation by Maloloy-on (2021) indicates that instructors are adaptable and open to change in this new normal. They regard themselves as learning facilitators and guarantee flexibility in meeting students' requirements. When it comes to teaching methods, most teachers choose online instruction, with blended instruction and modular instruction coming in last.

There is a strong need to improve certain areas in order that urgent and alternative measures can be planned and implemented. The division office can use the findings of this study in crafting interventions or proposing a plan of activities to satiate its policy lapses if there are any. School heads and supervisors in the schools division office of Escalante City may recommend doable interventions and propose a plan of activities via an action plan in order to formulate a viable roadmap to provide a clear guide to plans and programs to improve the level of technical skills and competence of sports officiating officials. Sports is now increasingly popular to spend free time, take care of one's health and physical and mental condition, and be entertained, especially with educators' burdensome heavy workloads of the new normal (Sabillo, S. et.al, 2023).

Zanescio (2020) points out that exercise is an affordable, accessible, and secure activity that can be incorporated into the daily routine of those under quarantine. To stop the spread of viruses, it is important to emphasize among physical education teachers to utilize technology to track exercises. Another difficulty that keeps individuals active without raising the incidence of contaminated subjects or the death rate is through social isolation relaxing policies. To detect and prevent social interaction with symptomatic people, routine testing must be promoted in gym areas. Additionally, it is crucial to keep the number of people in shared gym spaces to a minimum to maintain safe spacing between exercisers.

Lin et al. (2021) found that physical education (P.E.) has never received attention from education reform in China, despite the government and schools' strong investments in the development of distance learning (distance learning). Various issues have cropped up concerning this: First, the lack of resources for physical education courses. For university education, physical education courses are typically overlooked, as the emphasis is mostly on professional topic knowledge. This shows how the importance of physical education courses is frequently overlooked in many schools due to considerations over resource availability or other factors. Second, despite the purpose of distance learning to create an information-based platform and the investment of network teaching resources, P.E. teachers still need more information literacy.

Zheng (2021) posits that teachers must have access to computers, the Internet, and multimedia in addition to relying on their profession for basic information and other associated knowledge and abilities; and must be able to create multimedia-based courseware and teaching materials since this is a type of supplementary teaching tool. In the past, basic knowledge and skills only had to be taught outside of physical education classes, and there needed to be more usage of multimedia, computers, or networks. Because of this, few teachers choose to learn on their initiative. And lastly, because college P.E. courses are primarily practiced offline, they typically require specific venues and environments as the teaching basis, which distance learning may not provide. Regular teaching plans are challenging to implement online, and students' exercise conditions at home are constrained. The primary reason is that many physical education courses require appropriate locations, Sports learning movements must first be explained and demonstrated by the teacher, followed by repetition by the students to mimic the teacher's movements, and finally by the teacher's actual physical contact and correction of their movements so that the students may gradually learn the movements the teacher taught. Because of this, it sometimes becomes extremely difficult and impractical to complete a P.E. course via distance learning (SAGE Journals, 2021).

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study is anchored on the following theories: implementation theory by Thomas Palfrey in 2002, Social Support theory by Don Drennon Gala and Francis Cullen in 1994, and Theory of Difficulty by David Perkins in 2007. Implementation theory is a branch of economic theory that systematically examines how institutions created to

fulfill normative ends conform to those institutions. More specifically, it formally specifies organizational mechanisms that will ensure results compatible with that aim for a specific class of allocation issues (or domain of environments), provided the outcomes of any such mechanism arise from some definition of equilibrium behavior. As a matter of definition in the implementation theory literature, an institution is described as a mechanism, which is fundamentally a non-cooperative game. As a result, the approaches to this topic fall within the general domain of game theory (Jackson, 2001).

Another theory, called social support theory, was developed because of writings by Francis Cullen and Don Drennon-Gala, whom both took inspiration from various theoretical traditions. The core tenet of the idea is that instrumental, informational, and emotional assistance decreases the possibility of crime and delinquency. The idea considers macro and micro effects, highlighting how supportive cultures and relationships can lower delinquency and crime rates and personal delinquency and crime. Because efficient social control and rehabilitation rely on social support, social support is also implicated in the criminal justice and social control processes.

This theory is linked to the current study because MAPEH teachers were assessed to what extent they implement teaching and learning in MAPEH programs in the new normal. Another theory is a support system. Social support system theory is a crucial component of adolescent well-being and can significantly rehabilitate juvenile offenders. Communities with higher levels of social support also tend to have lower juvenile crime rates. This theory is essential in this study because it observes how the District High Offices, school heads, and master teachers support their instruction in the new normal, also, as to how they prioritize MAPEH in the different areas of their respective schools. In this study's concluding theory, David Perkin's theory of difficulty, he emphasized the significance of mastering challenging knowledge and abilities to advance to the next level of performance. He gave his pupils (teacher candidates) the assignment of creating a Theory of Difficulty (TOD) for a specific area of knowledge or talent (Madiba, 2010). This theory can be linked to the study because MAPEH teachers are assessed by their difficulty in this novel kind of set-up in teaching and must be considered towards the attainment of goals and success in teaching learners. To address the most challenging situation in the new normal the MAPEH teachers are facing.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the extent of implementation, level of support system, and level of difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the new normal in the two districts in a public secondary school. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the extent of implementation of MAPEH programs in the new normal according to the area of curriculum delivery, teacher development, learning resources; 2) the level of support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal according to the aforementioned areas; 3) level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal according to its components Music, Arts, P.E, and Health.

Methodology:

This section discusses the research design used, the participants of the study, the instruments used, the data-gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design. According to Dudovskiy (2017), descriptive research design attempts to determine, describe, or identify characteristics within the field of investigation). Descriptive research is a study of status and is widely used in education. Its value is based on the premise that problems can be solved and practices improved through observation, analysis, and description.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the forty-two (42) MAPEH teachers in the two districts in the public secondary schools during the school year 2021-2022, who composed the total number of respondents in this study and the elements or the group provided the data. Purposive sampling was used in the study. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in their surveys (Alchemer, 2021).

Instruments

The researcher utilized a self-made questionnaire for data collection. It was subjected to validity index of 4.82 interpreted as excellent and reliability index for the extent of implementation of MAPEH programs is 0.969, for the level of support system 0.957, and for the level of difficulties, 0.936, interpreted as excellent. It was composed of two (2) parts. Part I contains the respondents' profiles. Part II contains items intended to collect data on the extent of implementation and level of support system in the areas of curriculum delivery, teacher development, and learning resources. There were 5 items per area with a total of 50 items in all which the respondents rated as 5 - Very Great Extent, 4 - Great Extent, 3 - Moderate Extent, 2 - Low Extent and 1 - Very

Low Extent for the implementation, 5 -Very High , 4 – High Level, 3 – Moderate level, 2 – Low Level and 1 – Very Low Level for the support system and difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sent a request letter to the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study. After securing the approval, questionnaires were administered to the dry-run respondents and then to the actual respondents. Finally, the researcher then personally distributed the questionnaire to the respondents in their respective schools, which enabled him to explain the purpose of the study. The accomplished questionnaire was retrieved immediately after every administration. It took two weeks to finish distributing the survey instrument and two weeks for the retrieval because some respondents were from the mountain areas. Upon completion, the questionnaires were retrieved and subjected to statistical computation. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed with the aid of SPSS.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal regarding Curriculum Delivery, Teacher Development, and Learning Resources.

Objective No. 2, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to the level of the support system of MAPEH Programs in the new normal according to the aforementioned areas.

Objective No. 3 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean determine level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal according to its component Music, Arts, P.E, and Health.

Ethical Considerations

In accordance with R.A. No. 10173, otherwise known as the Data "Privacy Act of 2012," ensuring the well-being of the study respondents, ethical principles of Health and Safety, Anonymity, Confidentiality, and Honesty were considered. This research study was conducted adhering to the process imposed by the Division of Negros Occidental. The Schools Division Superintendent and Public Schools District Supervisors of the locale of the study signed a letter of approval. With the permission of the School Heads, the researcher sent a letter to the teacher-respondents informing them of the present research undertaking. Anonymity was guaranteed, not revealing the identity of the respondents. In addition, there will be no remuneration involved. Further, the data collected will be kept confidential until the completion and approval of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1
The Extent of implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Curriculum Delivery

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I use the modules coming from the CO/RO.	4.69	Very Great Extent
2. I prepare learning activity sheets.	4.21	Great Extent
3. I select the most relevant topics in the module.	4.19	Great Extent
4. I prepare a contextualized assessment	4.12	Great Extent
5. I use the platform that is agreed by the school	4.62	Very Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.37	Great Extent

Table 1 discloses the extent of implementation of MAPEH Programs in the new normal in terms of curriculum delivery. Generally, it obtained a mean score of 4.37, interpreted as great extent. Though all items got great and very great extent results, it can be veered that item no. 1 got the highest mean of 4.69, interpreted as great extent. This is on the use of modules coming from the CO/RO. On the other hand, item no. 4 got the lowest mean of 4.12. This is on preparing a contextualized assessment. It implies that there has been a gradual shift in the assessment process in the new normal. Some MAPEH teachers were trying to use their assessment strategies to motivate students' learning, and some were basing their assessments on references. The result above supports the study of Montero and Geducos (2022) that localized and contextualized activities have significantly improved the students' conceptual understanding of MAPEH.

Table 2
Extent of Implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the Area of Teacher Development

Items	Mean	Interpretation
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1. I attend webinars related to MAPEH	3.90	Great Extent
2. I engage myself to various training workshop	4.12	Great Extent
3. I update myself with content knowledge and pedagogy	4.24	Great Extent
4. I enhance my technological skills	4.21	Great Extent
5. I engage myself to demonstration teaching during LAC Sessions	4.12	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.12	Great Extent

Table 2 reveals the extent of implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal in terms of Teacher Development. As shown in the table, the extent of implementation in teacher development is great, having an overall of 4.12. This revealed that item no. 3, which states that "I update myself with content knowledge and pedagogy," got the highest mean of 4.24, interpreted as a great extent. However, item no. 1 got the lowest mean of 3.90, interpreted as great extent. It states that "I attend webinars related to MAPEH." It can be inferred that some MAPEH teachers need to be more engaged in remote webinars in their fields. Due to a lack of internet connectivity in some mountain areas, some MAPEH teachers could not attend. They make use of updating their selves if the seminars are echoed to them. This shares the findings of Barrera's (2022) investigation, which found that seminars and webinars were neither essential nor helpful in shaping teachers' perspectives on problems. Participation in training and webinars did not influence how acceptable coping mechanisms were for them.

Table 3
The Extent of Implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Learning Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I use electronic learning resources.	4.45	Great Extent
2. I download lessons from LRMS.	4.29	Great Extent
3. I make use of the social media in lesson development.	4.24	Great Extent
4. I contextualize lessons in MAPEH.	4.21	Great Extent
5. I make use of the different resources.	4.36	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.31	Great Extent

Table 3 presents results on the extent of implementation of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal in terms of learning resources. All items obtained a great extent of implementation with an overall mean of 4.31. In Table 5, it is also shown that the use of electronic learning resources got the highest mean of 4.45, interpreted as a great extent. Nevertheless, item no. 4 on the contextualization of MAPEH lessons got the lowest mean of 4.21 which is interpreted to a great extent. This indicates that some MAPEH Teachers need to relate the curriculum to the setting and situation of their school and make the competencies relevant, meaningful, and useful to learners. This could be why this item is rated lowest by the respondents. The results support Maloloy-on's (2021) findings which indicate that instructors were found to be adaptable and open to change in this new normal. The findings further showed that instructors regard themselves as learning facilitators and guarantee flexibility in attending to students' requirements. When it comes to teaching methods, most teachers chose online instruction, with blended instruction and modular instruction coming in last.

Table 4
The Level of Support System of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Curriculum Delivery

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. My school head provides technical assistance	3.67	High Level
2. I am provided with an appropriate platform for teaching the subject through MOOE	3.17	Moderate Level
3. We are working collaboratively with MAPEH Teachers	4.52	Very High Level
4. Our school has the quality assurance team	3.50	High Level
5. The master teachers are conducting demonstration teaching during LAC sessions	2.81	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.53	High Level

Table 4 provides results on the level of the support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal in terms of Curriculum delivery. The result came up with an overall mean score of 3.53. On the one hand, the highest mean score of 4.52, interpreted as a very high level, was in item no. 3 stating that MAPEH teachers are working collaboratively in delivering the curriculum. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 2.81, interpreted as a moderate level, was in item no. 5, stating that the master teachers are conducting demonstration teaching during LAC sessions. The support, instructional supervision, and technical assistance to MAPEH teachers in the new normal are the least prioritized. School heads and master teachers should keep an eye on this situation to improve the competence of MAPEH teachers. This study supports Donato's (2021) findings that monitoring and supervision are essential practices of school leaders to determine the various aspects of the school's performance and teachers' competencies.

Table 5
The Level of Support System of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Teacher Development

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Our school head encourages us to attend webinars related to MAPEH.	4.21	High Level
2. We are always conducting LAC Sessions	3.79	High Level
3. Our school head conducts seminar workshop in MAPEH.	2.71	Moderate Level
4. Our School Head encourages us to conduct Action Research.	3.74	High Level
5. Our School Head subscribes professional magazines.	2.50	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.39	Moderate Level

Table 5 provides results on the level of the support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal in terms of teacher development. An overall mean of 3.39, interpreted as a moderate level, is obtained, as revealed in the table. Item no. 1 has the highest mean of 4.21, which is interpreted as high level. This is on the school heads of the districts encouraging MAPEH teachers to attend webinars related to MAPEH in the new normal. However, item no. 5 had the lowest mean score of 2.50, interpreted as a moderate level. This is on the school heads' subscription to professional magazines. This implies that there are some schools that fell short in extensive coverage of local, state, and national K-12 educator news. They should discover expert analyses and opinions through objective and comprehensive reports. Gain insight into personalized learning and assessment in MAPEH. Sangalang (2017) contradicts this finding as his study revealed that a good educational system must prioritize teacher professional development. Both the head teachers and the teachers who responded firmly agreed that elements such as teachers' attitudes toward professional development, their assessment of its significance, and their assessment of task completion impact their engagement in the development. The head teachers who responded disagreed, but the teachers concurred that the demands of their jobs impact their engagement in professional development. The respondents overwhelmingly concurred that emotional demands impact teachers' participation in professional development. Both respondents firmly agreed that teachers' participation in professional development is influenced by their amount of autonomy and participation, as well as by management support, peer support, and deliberate learning assistance. Gallespin (2021), meanwhile, conforms to the result of this investigation which posits that the teachers experienced the support system through the webinars provided, the assistance of colleagues and housemates, and the help extended by parents to their children.

Table 6

The Level of Support System of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Learning Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. We have access in LRMS.	4.55	Very High Level
2. We are provided with various references.	3.93	High Level
3. We are provided with enough instructional materials.	3.52	High Level
4. We are provided with good internet connection.	2.29	Low Level
5. We are provided with our teaching needs through MOOE.	3.07	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.47	Moderate Level

Table 6 shows the level of the support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal in learning resources. An overall mean of 3.47, Item no. 1 had the highest mean of 4.55, interpreted as a very high level. This is on the accessibility of MAPEH teachers in the Learning Resources Management and Development System. However, item no. 4 had the lowest mean score of 2.29 interpreted low level. This is on the provision of a good internet connection for MAPEH teachers. This implies that the access to information and resources in the district is low, and it is essential for schools that might need more money to get physical materials for every subject that they need, particularly in MAPEH. Access to the internet typically allows schools to get the information they need. The study of Tagaytay *et al.* (2017) found that teachers' use of digital computer technology became a source of anxiety among learners instead of adding and enriching learning. The lack of school funding for computer units and computer laboratories also added to the struggle of educators and students. To deal with the Digital Divide that is evident in their school, the teachers would utilize their own money to buy portable Internet devices, buy credits for these devices, and even lend their laptops to students so they have "hands-on" experience with computers and the internet. Students shared that they would have to travel long distances to be able to use the internet when these facilities should have been available in their school so that they could learn how to use them for coursework and in their future professions. The students added that they feel inferior compared to students in private schools who are well-provided with computer and Internet facilities. The study's findings bear significant implications for education and learning and policy formation for educational institutions in the public sector to address the presence of the Digital Divide.

Table 7

The Level of Difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Music

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Assessing the progress of students' capability in playing musical instruments due to lack of musical instruments	3.74	High Level
2. Mastering the competencies and skills in Music with sense of	3.48	Moderate Level

commitment		
3. Improving appropriate accompaniment to selected music which are not available in the district	3.55	High Level
4. Evaluating performance tasks (e.g., musical instruments and music from the other countries)	3.52	High Level
Contextualizing music lessons	3.33	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.52	High Level

Table 7 shows the level of difficulty of MAPEH programs in the new normal in Music. An overall mean of 3.52, interpreted as a high level, is obtained, as revealed in the table. Item no. 5 had the lowest mean of 3.33, interpreted as a moderate level. This is on contextualizing music lessons. However, item no. 1 had the highest mean of 3.74, which is on the difficulty of assessing the progress of students' capability in playing musical instruments. This finding implies that actual and direct purposeful experience in teaching music, particularly in playing musical instruments, is needed to achieve music competency. Higher offices must provide the basic needs of MAPEH teachers to achieve competency in MELCS as well as training and workshops in contextualizing music lessons. This result conforms to the study of Daga (2020) that high school MAPEH teachers have highlighted the following music-related subjects or competencies where they need the training to improve. From the fourteen (14) competencies that the teacher respondents indicated, these subjects or competencies emerged as the top five. The top item on the list, chosen by 30 (27.27 percent) of the 110 respondents, is "Teaching How to Play Musical Instruments (Guitar, Violin, Keyboard, Indigenous/Ethnic Musical Instruments)." The second, chosen by 28 respondents (24.45%), was "Understanding Music across Periods, Cultures & Places." The third topic, "Reading Musical Notes," was chosen by 547 responders (65.90%). The fourth topic was "Identifying/interpreting and Using Different Musical Symbols," which was identified by 24 (21.82 percent) respondents. The fifth topic was "Mastering the Fundamentals/Rudiments of Music," which was identified by 16 (14.54 percent) of the MAPEH teachers. For them to be able to teach the skill to the learners, it was discovered that learning to play a different musical instrument was the competency that was most in need.

Table 8

The Level of Difficulties of MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Arts

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Developing students' artistic skills due to lack of teaching art materials	3.50	High Level
2. Improving the learning resources in arts	3.38	Moderate Level
3. Working with colleagues who are teaching arts to share relevant concepts and ideas	3.07	Moderate Level
4. Comparing the characteristics of artworks produced in the different art periods due to lack of resources	3.19	Moderate Level
5. Validating learners' outputs	3.33	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.30	Moderate Level

Table 8 provides results on the level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in Arts. An overall mean of 3.30, interpreted as a moderate degree, has been obtained, as shown in the table. Item no. 3 has the lowest mean of 3.07, interpreted as a moderate level. This is on working with colleagues teaching arts to share relevant concepts and ideas. However, item no. 1 has the highest mean score of 3.50 or high level. This is on developing students' artistic skills due to a need for teaching art materials. This connotes that actual and direct purposeful experience in teaching arts, particularly artistic skills, is needed to achieve competency in arts. Higher offices are challenged and focused on developing the basic needs of MAPEH teachers to achieve competency in MELCS as well as training and workshops in contextualizing arts lessons. This finding confirms the study of Daga (2020) that the high school MAPEH teachers have identified the following topics or competencies in teaching art that they need training for enhancement purposes. These topics or competencies came out as the top five out of the fifteen (15) competencies that the high school teachers had identified. Number 1 was on "Using Advanced Technologies in Graphic Designing/Using ICT in Art/Pixel Art/ Digital Art(Painting/Drawing/Printing/Photo-editing)"; Number 2 was on "Teaching Different Crafts (basketry, weaving, cross-stitching, pottery, recycling, decorating, cosmetology, etc.)"; Number 3 was on "Mastering the Fundamentals of Sketching, Drawing, Painting, Sculpture/Carving"; Number 4 was on "Writing Contextualized lesson Plans for art Education"; and Number 5 was on "Teaching the Elements & Principles of Art." As regards the competency with the highest percentage distribution, the study identified that MAPEH teachers popularly need training on the advanced techniques or means of doing artwork, such as using the computer and its related applications. Just like teaching music, the findings imply that most teachers lack technical and content knowledge in teaching art education to high school learners. Hence, they need the conduct capacity building for them; especially those untrained ones because they are new to teaching.

Table 9

The Level of Difficulties in MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of PE

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Receiving performance tasks such as video presentations and vlogs of students due to lack of gadget	3.29	Moderate Level

2. Correcting students' execution of a particular skill	3.19	Moderate Level
3. Initiating students' participation in active recreation	3.17	Moderate Level
4. Assessing any physical activities (e.g., various sports, dance genres and exercises)	3.10	Moderate Level
5. Enhancing learners' skills	3.24	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderate Level

Table 9 shows the level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal in Physical Education. An overall mean of 3.20 is interpreted as a moderate level, as revealed in the table. Item no. 4 had the lowest mean score of 3.10, interpreted as a moderate level on assessing various physical activities in the new normal. Item no. 1 had the highest mean of 3.29, interpreted as a moderate level of students receiving performance tasks due to a lack of gadgets. This implies that the MAPEH teachers need help to collect the tasks they gave to students in achieving the competencies in PE. Students need gadgets to do the assigned tasks of MAPEH teachers. Since it is remote learning, parents or DepEd must give attention to this matter to improve and achieve the performance tasks of students in PE. The results above contradict the study of Sibag and Arambulo (2022). The functions of these emergent modes in disseminating information were sending announcements, receiving announcements, sending reminders, receiving reminders, seeking approval/permission, receiving approval, sending reports, and receiving reports. In terms of urgency, it was revealed that SMS was important when sending and receiving announcements, sending and receiving reminders, receiving approval, and sending and receiving reports, while internal phone call was for seeking approval/permission. In terms of validity, the overall result revealed that letters were important in receiving announcements, sending and receiving reminders, seeking approval/permission and receiving approval, and sending and receiving reports, while memoranda played a vital role in sending announcements. For frequency, memorandum and letters were the important modes. In terms of availability, memoranda, SMS, and face-to-face conversation were all important in receiving announcements, while memorandum and face-to-face conversation were for seeking approval/permission, receiving approval, and sending reports. Lastly, in terms of accessibility, memoranda, SMS, and student assistants were the highest-rated modes. All functions except receiving announcements relied on student assistants; only sending and receiving announcements were for SMS, and receiving approval and receiving reports were for memoranda.

Table 10

The Level of Difficulties in MAPEH Programs in the New Normal according to the area of Health

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a Health Teacher, I have difficulties in...		
1. Giving other enrichment activities to have a deeper and thorough understanding in learning health	3.00	Moderate Level
2. Promoting programs and policies to prevent and control diseases	3.21	Moderate Level
3. Strategizing and suggesting healthy alternatives	3.17	Moderate Level
4. Developing and imposing quality and structure of performance tasks in Health due to pandemic safety protocols and health issues	3.19	Moderate Level
5. Monitoring learners' health practices	3.52	High Level
Overall Mean	3.22	Moderate Level

Table 10 presents the results on the level of difficulties of MAPEH programs in the new normal in health. An overall mean score of 3.22 is interpreted as a moderate level, as shown in the table. Item no. 1 had the lowest mean of 3.00, interpreted as a moderate level stating that the health teacher has difficulty giving other enrichment activities to have a deeper and thorough understanding of learning health. However, item no. 5 had the highest mean of 3.52 interpreted high level stating that the health teacher has difficulty monitoring learners' health practices. This implies that MAPEH teachers are making an extra effort to support their schools in monitoring health indices and require action from parents in this new normal. The school head is also keeping his eye on the learners. Daga (2020) confirms this result in that the competencies in health need more training for enhancement purposes. These topics or competencies came out as the top five out of the ten (10) identified competencies by the teacher-respondents, as follows: Providing First Aid Services/Life-Saving Skills/Basic Life Support Techniques; Health Issues and Trends; Planning for Health Career; Teaching Precautionary & Safety Measures/Injury Prevention; and Writing Contextualized Lesson Plans in Health Education. The health competency with the highest frequency distribution was on teaching learners how to respond to an emergency to save lives by applying first aid, life-saving support, and techniques. This was identified by 16 out of the 110 high school teacher-respondents, who comprise 14.54%. Technical and content knowledge in teaching the skills, as mentioned earlier, is very important for teachers because they are basic for survival, especially since the Philippines is prone to natural calamities. These competencies can be utilized by learners not only to save themselves but also to help others in times of emergency. Hence, the need to address this as a priority consideration for capability building or re-tooling of high school MAPEH teachers, including the other identified competencies.

Conclusions:

Based on the results of the study, the extent of implementation in the areas of curriculum delivery, teacher development, and learning resources were great. The level of support system in curriculum delivery was great while in teacher development and learning resources was moderate. The level of difficulties in Music was high while in the areas of Arts, PE and Health were moderate. It is therefore concluded that MAPEH programs were greatly implemented. The modules coming from the CO/RO were utilized accordingly. MAPEH teachers are up to date with the current professional standards and are willing to be equipped with different teaching strategies and approaches in the new normal. MAPEH Teachers provide e-learning resources for learners in their respective learning delivery modalities, and they see themselves as facilitators of learning and ensure flexibility in dealing with students' needs. The support system of MAPEH teachers is evident by working collaboratively. This paper calls for school heads, master teachers, and MAPEH teachers should continue to work together to sustain the implementation and support system of MAPEH programs in the new normal at their respective stations; District and school management should prioritize the improvement and availability of teaching art materials and musical instruments and allocate budget to it; and Division Education Program Supervisor (DEPS) in MAPEH offer seminars and training on the competencies needed.

Acknowledgement

This paper could not have been realized without the help of various people; thus, the researcher thanks them for helping him who may contribute big and small ways for the completion of this endeavor.

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